

NOTES

Studies on Dioxomolybdenum(VI) Complexes of some N-O Donors

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CHEMISTRY of molybdenum(VI) has assumed immense importance because of its presence in certain metalloenzymes and also because of its capacity to effect nitrogen fixation when present in appropriate donor surroundings¹⁻⁴. In the present study we report the syntheses and characterization of several complexes MoO₂²⁺ species in mixed N-O donor surroundings and incorporating Cl⁻ in the first co-ordination sphere. Some of these complexes possess the general characteristics of a molybdenum complex capable of fixing nitrogen.

A number of molybdenum(VI) complexes containing the MoO₂²⁺ cation of some aromatic acidhydrazides have been synthesized and characterized. Complexes of dioxomolybdenum(VI), with the Schiff bases derived from the aromatic acidhydrazides as the amine components and diacetylmonoxime and salicylaldehyde as the carbonyl components, have also been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, uv-visible, and IR spectral study, magnetic susceptibility measurement and measurement of conductance in solution. Though, the oxomolybdenum source used in all the preparations was (NH₄)₂[MoOCl₆] containing the MoO³⁺ species, all the isolated compounds contain the MoO₂²⁺-cation containing Mo(VI), due to oxidation of the MoO³⁺ moiety by atmospheric air. Most of the compounds contain coordinated chloride ions.

Experimental

Ammonium oxopentachloromolybdate was prepared by standard method⁵.

The complexes were prepared by the following general method.

The ligands (0.002 mole) were taken in alcoholic solution by refluxing and ammonium oxopentachloromolybdate (0.001 mole) added directly to the solution, refluxed for 1½-2 hours and cooled. The solid complexes formed were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over fused CaCl₂.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. B.D.H. grade or of equivalent quality.

The ligands are depicted as follows

A, B, C, D = LH and E, F, G = L'H₂

The analytical results of the complexes along with the magnetic moment and electronic spectra, were reported in Table 1. Electronic spectra in solution were recorded in a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer, while the IR spectra were obtained in KBr-matrix in a Beckman IR 20A spectrometer with CsBr optics. Mull spectra in nujol were taken in a spectro MOM 201 (Hungarian) spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in a Guoy balance using CoHg(SCN)₄ as the calibrant.

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TABLE 1

Ligand	Compound	% of Metal found	% of Nitrogen found	% of Halide found	M. P. °C	Colour	Mol. wt.	Absorption spectra λ_{max}
A	MoO ₂ (C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ O)Cl ₂ (I)	27.61 (27.42)	11.90 (12.00)	20.10 (20.28)	210	Orange yellow	350	335 in methanol
B	MoO ₂ (C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ O)Cl ₂ (II)	29.20 (28.65)	8.46 (8.35)	21.12 (21.19)	250	Orange yellow	335	305 in mull
C	MoO ₂ (C ₇ H ₇ N ₃ O ₂)Cl (III)	29.97 (30.62)	8.82 (8.93)	11.45 (11.32)	250	Buff coloured	313.5	315 in mull
D	MoO ₂ (C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ O)Cl ₂ (IV)	27.19 (27.42)	11.85 (12.00)	20.14 (20.28)	235	Orange yellow	350	290 in methanol
E	MoO ₂ (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂)Cl (V)	22.80 (22.93)	10.12 (10.03)	8.60 (8.48)	235	Brown	418.5	325 in mull
F	MoO ₂ (C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂)Cl (VI)	24.18 (23.79)	6.85 (6.94)	8.85 (8.79)	270	Brown	403.5	300 in methanol
G	MoO ₂ (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂)Cl (VII)	23.24 (22.93)	10.15 (10.03)	8.42 (8.48)	Above 300	Brownish Black	418.5	285 in 385 methanol

The figures in the parentheses indicate the calculated values.

Discussions

MoO₂⁺² complexes of the acid hydrazides :

All the complexes isolated possess the general formula MoO₂LHCl₂, where LH is a hydrazide molecule acting in the keto form. All the complexes are diamagnetic in nature, indicating the presence of Mo(VI) species. The strong IR bands in the region 945-975 cm⁻¹ give evidence of the presence of the MoO₂⁺² in all the complexes. The lowering of the ν >C=O band of the acidhydrazides on complex formation, points to co-ordination through the carbonyl oxygen. The shift of the N-H stretching mode towards lower frequency in the complexes indicates co-ordination from the terminal -NH₂ of the hydrazide moiety⁷. All the hydrazides co-ordinate in the keto form, which is concluded from the presence of two Cl⁻ ions per MoO₂⁺² species, as well as from the absence of a very strong band around 1590-1600 cm⁻¹ due to the ν >C=N band, which would have appeared, if the ligands were present in the enol form.

Complexes II-IV (Table 1) react with heterocyclic bases like pyridine and picolines to yield species of the general nature [MoO₂(L)(B)₂]Cl, in which, the hydrazide is present in the enolic form (L⁻ representing the enolate) with the Cl⁻ ion existing outside the first sphere of co-ordination. This has been confirmed by the disappearance of the band due to the co-ordinated >C=O group and the appearance of an intense band around 1590-1600 cm⁻¹ due to the >C=N stretch appearing as a result of enolisation

MoO₂⁺² complexes of the Schiff bases :

The complexes of Schiff bases, obtained by the condensation of the carbonyl group of salicylaldehyde with the terminal -NH₂ of benzoylhydrazide, *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazide and *p*-aminobenzoylhydrazide, have the general formula MoO₂(L'H)Cl, where L'H₂ represent a molecule of Schiff base. In the Schiff base derived from *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazide, the condensation takes place from the ring amino-group of the hydrazide and is proved by the disappearance of the ring -NH₂ proton peak at 4 δ ⁸ (as observed in the pmr spectrum of the hydrazide in CDCl₃) in the pmr spectrum (with TMS as standard) of the Schiff base in CDCl₃. In the complexes the ligands acted as monoprotic tridentate donors with the Cl⁻ occupying the sixth position in the co-ordination octahedra. In the complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and the acidhydrazides, bonding takes place from the azomethine nitrogen, the carbonyl oxygen and the deprotonated phenolic oxygen⁹. MoO₂⁺² complexes of the ligands obtained by condensing diacetylmonoxime with benzoyl, salicyl and *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazides have the general formula MoO₂(L''H)Cl. The IR data indicate that, in these complexes the bonding takes place from the hydrazide carbonyl oxygen, the azomethine nitrogen (indicated by a shift of ν >C=N from 1570-80 cm⁻¹ to 1560-45 cm⁻¹ region) and the oxime nitrogen (indicated by the shift of ν >C=N from 1425-35 cm⁻¹ to 1475-45 cm⁻¹ region)⁹.

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"Physicochemical Studies on the Composition and Stability of the Complexes of UO_2^{++} ion and Ag(I) with N-Glycylglycine"

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ON account of the increased significance of the amino acids in pharmaceutical, biological and industrial field, considerable interest regarding their electrochemical behaviour has been shown in the past two decades. Saxena and co-workers have made extensive study on the electrometric behaviour of some of the amino acids¹⁻². This communication reports the polarographic determination of the stability constants of the complexes of UO_2^{++} ion with N-Glycylglycine and also the determination of composition and stability constants of Ag(I) complexes of N-Glycylglycine at 30° and 40° by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques. There is, however, no reference in the literature on the study of the present system.

Experimental

N-Glycylglycine was supplied by B.D.H. chemicals Poole England and all other chemicals used were of AnalR grade.

In case of the polarographic study of N-glycylglycine complexes with uranyl ion, the concentration of UO_2^{++} ion was 1 mM in the presence of 0.1M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton X-100. The concentration of ligand was varied from 0.02 to 0.13M.

Toshniwal polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the current voltage curves. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 0.1 M NaClO_4 : $m=2.953$ mgm/sec, $t=2.5$ sec/drop, $h=44.0$ cms and -0.4 V vs S.C.E.

pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal pH meter (Type CL-46) with a glass electrode assembly.

Conductance was measured on electronic eye type conductometer (L.B.R.; W.T.W. Germany). The temperature was controlled by a Universal thermostat (type U_3).

Results and Discussion

Polarographic Study :

The current-voltage curves of UO_2^{++} ion in presence of different concentrations of N-glycylglycine are plotted at 30°. In each case a single well defined cathodic wave appeared. All the plots of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ vs $-E_{de}$ yielded straight lines and the slopes agreed with the reversibility of the reduction. The cathodic shift in $E_{1/2}$ coupled with decrease in diffusion current on increasing N-glycylglycine concentration shows the complex formation with UO_2^{++} ion. The plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ was found to be linear indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction of UO_2^{++} complexes of N-Glycylglycine.

The curvature obtained in the plot of $-E_{1/2}$ Vs. $-\log C_x$ showed the successive complex formation and hence the method of DeFord and Hume^{3,4} was adopted for deriving various functions $F_j(X)$: From the experimental data, the complexity function $F_j(X)$ which is polynomial in (X) , is set up; the coefficients of the latter are required β_n . The graphical extrapolation reduces the polynomial equation to N-equations from which the corresponding β_n are obtained and are given below :

UO_2^{++} -N-glycylglycine complexes at 30°
 $\beta_1 = 1, \beta_2 = 280.$

Potentiometric Studies :

The stoichiometry of the reaction between Ag^+ and N-glycylglycine were determined by potentiometric titrations of mixtures of the reactions in various ratio against standard NaOH (0.1M).

Addition of an equimolar concentration of Ag^+ greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve (Fig. 1) as a result of complex formation and consequently a considerable lowering in buffer region starts. The inflection at $m=1$ suggesting the formation of 1 : 1 complex. When 2 moles of ligand are added to 1 mole of Ag^+ the inflection at one mole of NaOH per mole of metal ion again indicates the formation of 1 : 1 complex.

Fig. 2 represents the change in conductivity when solutions of ligand were titrated against AgNO_3 solution. The breaks in the titration curves suggest the formation of 1 : 1 complex.